

POTENTIAL OF PAPAIN NANOFLOWERS FOR INHIBITION OF BIOFILM-FORMING BACTERIA IN THE FOOD SECTOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13847178>

Abstract. *The increasing prevalence of biofilm forming bacteria in the food sector poses significant challenges to food safety and quality. Papain, a cysteine protease enzyme derived from papaya, has emerged as a promising agent for combating these resilient microbial communities. This paper explores the potential of papain nano-flowers, which enhance the enzyme's stability and activity, in preventing biofilm formation by various pathogenic bacteria. The review synthesizes the current research demonstrating papain's efficacy against biofilms, particularly those formed by Staphylococcus aureus and Streptococcus mutants and discusses its applications in food safety and preservation.*

Keywords: food safety, Papain enzyme, Nanoflower, Bio-film, Sustainability.

Introduction

Biofilms are structured communities of microorganisms that adhere to surfaces and are encased in a self-produced extracellular matrix. They are notoriously difficult to eradicate and can lead to significant food safety issues, including contamination and spoilage. The food industry is particularly vulnerable to biofilm-related challenges, as these microbial communities can form on food contact surfaces, equipment, and within food products themselves [1]. Traditional antimicrobial agents often fail to penetrate these biofilms effectively, necessitating the exploration of alternative strategies for biofilm control [2].

Papain, a proteolytic enzyme known for its antibacterial properties, has shown promising results in disrupting biofilms (Fig. 1). Research indicates that papain can hydrolyse the extracellular matrix components of biofilms, leading to bacterial detachment and reduced biomass [3,4].

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the synthesis of Papain

For instance, studies have demonstrated that papain significantly decreases the biomass of *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms, outperforming conventional agents like lysostaphin. Furthermore, papain’s ability to degrade the peptide bonds in salivary pellicles suggests its potential application in oral health, particularly in preventing dental biofilms [5,6].

The immobilization of papain onto nanostructured carriers, such as chitosan and magnetic nanoparticles, has been explored to enhance its stability and reusability in food applications [7,8]. These papain nanoflowers not only improve the enzyme’s catalytic efficiency but also facilitate targeted delivery, making them effective in preventing biofilm formation on food surfaces (Fig. 2) [9]. The incorporation of papain in food packaging materials has also been investigated, showing significant reduction in biofilm-forming bacteria on meat products [10].

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the mechanism for the development of Papain nano-flower

Conclusion

The synthesis of papain conjugated nano-flowers represent a promising strategy for combating microbial biofilms in the food industry.

The sturdy structure of these nanoflowers allows them to effectively control biofilms while limiting the development of resistance bacteria.

Papain conjugated nano-flowers have the potential to revolutionize bio-film control practice leading to safer and higher quality food product for consumer.

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